

Supplementary Materials for

How Does Corporate Involvement Shape Open Source Projects? A Large-Scale Empirical Study

This supplementary material presents the additional figures produced by the study's experiments that are not shown in the main paper. The figures and tables that appear in the paper are not reproduced here. Each figure is shown one per page. The four corporate-involvement levels are set by a project's Total Corporate Participation (TCP), the share of its commits from corporate email domains: Community-Driven (TCP [0%, 20%]), Moderate-Balanced Corporate [20%, 50%), Majority-Corporate [50%, 70%), and Corporate-Dominated [70%, 100%].

Contents

1 RQ1: Project structure and practices	2
1.1 Contribution structure	2
1.2 Contributor retention and project stability	8
1.3 Development practices	11
1.4 Types of development work	15
2 RQ2: Contributor dynamics	17
2.1 Newcomer-to-core pipeline and retention	17
2.2 Working-time patterns	23
2.3 Contributor personas	25
2.4 Collaboration network	27
3 RQ3: Change over a project's life	29
3.1 Corporate-involvement trajectories	29

RQ1: Project structure and practices

Contribution structure

Figure 1: Top-company share (CR1), the share of a project's corporate commits from its single largest company, by corporate-involvement level. The median rises from 51% in Community-Driven projects to 90% in Corporate-Dominated ones.

Figure 2: Share of projects in each Herfindahl-Hirschman Index band, by corporate-involvement level. The high-HHI band grows from 60% of Community-Driven projects to 98% of Corporate-Dominated ones, so corporate commits come from fewer companies as involvement rises.

Figure 3: Elephant factor, the fewest companies whose commits make up half of a project's corporate commits, by corporate-involvement level. The median is one at every level, with the widest spread among Community-Driven projects.

Figure 4: Share of a project’s core contributors who commit from a corporate domain, by corporate-involvement level. The median rises from 8% in Community-Driven projects to 80% in Corporate-Dominated ones.

Figure 5: Spearman correlations among the contributor-structure metrics. Most pairs are weakly correlated, with a few related families such as activity volume, team size, and the inverse Gini-to-core-share pair.

Figure 6: Hierarchical clustering of the contributor-structure metrics by correlation, with the redundancy cut at an absolute correlation of 0.7. Only a few pairs merge below the cut, so the retained metrics are largely non-redundant.

Contributor retention and project stability

Figure 7: Mean contributor join rate over normalized project life, by corporate-involvement level. The join rate is highest in Community-Driven projects throughout and lowest in Corporate-Dominated ones.

Figure 8: Mean contributor leave rate over normalized project life, by corporate-involvement level. Attrition rises over a project's life at every level and is lower under higher corporate involvement for most of the lifetime.

Figure 9: Density of projects in join-rate by leave-rate space, by corporate-involvement level, with the four stability quadrants marked. Higher corporate involvement shifts projects toward the low-turnover Stable region.

Development practices

Figure 10: Pull-request and issue lifecycle metrics by corporate-involvement level (PR merge rate, PR merge time, issue close time, weekly issue responsiveness). Differences across levels are small, with Community-Driven projects marginally faster and more responsive.

Figure 11: Share of projects classified as mirrors across mirror-cutoff thresholds, by corporate-involvement level. Prevalence depends heavily on the threshold, and Corporate-Dominated projects are flagged most often.

Commit Message Discipline by Corporate Involvement Tier

Figure 12: Commit-message metrics by corporate-involvement level (subject length, issue-reference rate, Conventional Commits rate, external-tracker rate). More corporate projects write slightly longer messages but reference issues and adopt Conventional Commits less.

Figure 13: Median rate of GitHub-native versus external-tracker issue references in commit messages, by corporate-involvement level. Commit messages point to GitHub issues at every level and almost never to external trackers.

Types of development work

Figure 14: Median share of non-merge commits that are corrective, adaptive, and perfective, by corporate-involvement level. The mix is nearly identical across levels.

Attributable commits only (corporate + community). Masked / noreply commits excluded: 4.6-29.6% of non-merge human commits per tier (pooled). Numbers in bands are % of the bar.

Figure 15: Corporate versus community share of each work type, by corporate-involvement level. The corporate share of every work type grows with involvement, and community contributions are nearly absent in Corporate-Dominated projects.

RQ2: Contributor dynamics

Newcomer-to-core pipeline and retention

Figure 16: Cumulative incidence of a contributor reaching core over weeks since first commit, by corporate-involvement level, for the full sample (left) and an age-matched 2014-2018 cohort (right). Contributors reach core sooner and more often under lower corporate involvement, and part of the gap remains after matching.

Figure 17: Kaplan-Meier core-contributor retention over days since first commit, by corporate-involvement level. Retention rises with corporate involvement, the reverse of the ordering for reaching core.

Figure 18: Cox hazard ratios for core-contributor departure relative to Community-Driven projects, with 95% confidence intervals. All three corporate levels sit near 0.71 to 0.73, indicating longer retention.

Figure 19: Cox hazard ratios for reaching core relative to Community-Driven projects, for the full sample and the age-restricted cohort. The hazard of reaching core falls as corporate involvement rises.

Figure 20: Per-project weekly rate at which newcomers become core contributors, by corporate-involvement level. The rate is broadly similar across levels.

Figure 21: Project-level share of one-time newcomers (left) and conversion among returning newcomers (right), by corporate-involvement level. Higher corporate involvement is associated with fewer one-time newcomers and more returners reaching core.

Working-time patterns

Figure 22: Office, weekend, and night commit ratios per contributor, by corporate-involvement level. Higher corporate involvement is associated with more office-hour commits and fewer weekend and night commits.

Figure 23: Within-project difference between corporate and personal contributors in office-hour commit share, pooled and by corporate-involvement level. Corporate contributors commit a slightly higher share during office hours at every level.

Contributor personas

Figure 24: Z-scored profile of each of the seven contributor personas on the six clustering axes. The personas separate along distinct activity, timing, tenure, and brokerage axes.

Figure 25: Persona mix within each corporate-involvement level. The founder long-tenure persona grows with corporate involvement while the off-hours bursty and steady late-joiner personas shrink.

Collaboration network

Figure 26: Normalized co-participation-network measures by corporate-involvement level. Network shape shifts from modular, centralized collaboration toward a denser core-periphery structure as involvement rises.

Figure 27: Distribution of pull-request co-participation modularity Q , by corporate-involvement level. Median modularity declines from 0.32 in Community-Driven projects to 0.26 in Corporate-Dominated ones.

RQ3: Change over a project's life

Corporate-involvement trajectories

Figure 28: Mean corporate-commit share over normalized project life for the three trajectory patterns. Rising projects climb, Falling projects decline, and Flat projects stay near constant.

Figure 29: Composition of trajectory patterns within each corporate-involvement level. Falling trajectories are far more common once corporate involvement is present than in Community-Driven projects.

Figure 30: Share of projects with a significant Mann-Kendall trend under the real data versus a time-shuffled null. The real rate of 52.6% far exceeds the null rate of 4.8%, so the trends are real signal.

Figure 31: Cluster-count diagnostics (silhouette, gap statistic, and bootstrap stability) for the trajectory clustering. $k=3$ is the largest setting that keeps bootstrap stability above 0.75.